

Synthesis of Some Pyrazolothiazolidino-2-ones. Part-I

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Synthesis of 1-phenyl-5-aryl- Δ^2 -pyrazolino[3,4-d]thiazolidin-2-one (12) and its substituted derivatives are reported. Some of them show antifungal properties.

THIAZOLIDINONES and their derivatives are well known for their biological activity¹. Only a small number of fused thiazolidinones are however, known^{2,3} to possess this activity. As some thiazolidinones^{4,5} and pyrazolines⁶ are reported for antifungal activity, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise pyrazoline ring condensed thiazolidinones and screen their biological activity.

For achieving this aim the rhodanine which contained thiazolidinone ring was condensed with aromatic aldehydes to give its benzylidene derivatives. These were condensed with phenylhydrazine in glacial acetic acid or absolute ethanol in presence of sodium acetate. The intermediate phenylhydrazones eluded isolation as they underwent subsequent cyclisation⁷ and desulphurisation to give 1-phenyl-5-aryl- Δ^2 -pyrazolino[3,4-d]thiazolidino-2-one (12) or its derivatives. The ir spectra of these compounds (12-14) show bands at 1650-1710 (C=O), 1580-1610 (C=N) and 3110 cm^{-1} (weak bonded OH). The absence of absorption at 1450 cm^{-1} (thiureide) indicates desulphurisation during the reaction. The compounds (12-14) were also obtained from the benzylidene derivatives of 2-imino-4-thiazolidinone. The formations of these compounds exhibits hydrolytic removal of the imine group during the reaction.

To study the scope of this reaction benzylidene derivatives of 2-imino-4-thiazolidinone were condensed with *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine which afforded pyrazolothiazolidinones, (16 and 17). But when benzylidene derivatives of 2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidinone or 2-imino-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone were experimented, they did not give the corresponding pyrazolothiazolidinones. The stability of these compounds towards heat supports their structure as Δ^2 -pyrazoline and the possibility of Δ^3 (12a) structure is ruled out⁸.

The fungicidal activity of the compounds 12, 13 and 14 was determined by the poisoned-food technique⁹ at various concentrations. It was found that all the three compounds inhibited the growth of the test fungus *Aspergillus flavus*. The compound 12 was found to act as spore suppressant.

Pmr spectrum of the compound 12 was recorded. As the solubility of the compound was poor in CDCl_3 , the spectrum obtained from the filtrate was unsatisfactory and against background noise, the aromatic peaks can be seen at δ 6.5-7.3. The solubility of the compound 13 was also poor in CDCl_3 , a few drops of methanol- D_4 was added and even then the spectrum was ill defined. The only significant part that could be interpreted was the presence of methoxy group at δ 3.6-3.7 (3H) and aromatic protons at δ 7.0-7.2 (9H).

- 1 X=S, R=phenyl
- 2 X=S, R=*p*-methoxyphenyl
- 3 X=S, R=*p*-chlorophenyl
- 4 X=S, R=*o*-hydroxyphenyl
- 5 X=NH, R=phenyl
- 6 X=NH, R=*p*-chlorophenyl
- 7 X=NH, R=*p*-nitrophenyl
- 8 X=NPh, R=phenyl
- 9 X=NPh, R=*p*-methoxyphenyl

- 10 X=S, R=phenyl, Y=phenyl
- 11 X=NH, R=phenyl, Y=phenyl
- 12 X=O, R=Phenyl, Y=phenyl
- 13 X=O, R=*p*-methoxyphenyl, Y=phenyl
- 14 X=O, R=*p*-chlorophenyl, Y=phenyl
- 15 X=O, R=*p*-nitrophenyl, Y=phenyl
- 16 X=O, R=phenyl, Y=*p* nitrophenyl
- 17 X=O, R=*p*-chlorophenyl, Y=*p*-nitrophenyl

12a

TABLE I

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Colour	Yield %	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				Knorr's colour test*	
					C	H	N	S	With ferric chloride	With chromic acid
12	220-21	Bright red	50%	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	64.56 (65.05)	4.51 (4.4)	14.5 (14.2)	10.1 (10.8)	Light green	Violet
13	283-84	Dull red	50%	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	62.15 (62.79)	4.7 (4.61)	11.85 (12.0)	9.1 (9.8)	Light green	Violet
14	272-273	Shining bright red	50%	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	58.1 (58.3)	3.2 (3.6)	12.5 (12.7)	9.0 (9.7)	Light green	Violet
15	268	Shining brownish black	50%	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₃ S	57.6 (58.1)	4.12 (3.6)	18.15 (16.9)	9.3 (10.04)	Bluish green	Violet
16	307	Brown	45%	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ S	57.07 (56.4)	4.3 (3.5)	15.5 (13.52)	9.4 (10.04)	Green	Violet
17	300	Black	30%	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₂ SCl	52.53 (51.30)	3.8 (3.9)	14.76 (15.2)	10.5 (11.1)	Deep green	Violet

* Knorr, *Ann.*, 1887, 238, 200; L. Chas. Raiford and W. J. Peterson, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1936, 1, 545.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. The uv and ir spectra were recorded at Chemical Laboratory, Magadh University on a Beckmann-DU-2 and Perkin Elmer-577 spectrophotometer, respectively. The pmr spectra were recorded at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow on a Varian A-60, A-90 apparatus in CDCl₃ (chemical shifts expressed in δ , J 90 MHz and the reference-standard is TMS).

1-Phenyl-5-aryl- Δ^2 -pyrazolino[3, 4-d]thiazolidin-2-one (12): Method A: A mixture of 5-benzalrhodanine (1) (2 g, 0.01 mol) in dry ethanol (20 ml), sodium acetate (2 g) and phenylhydrazine, (2 ml) was refluxed over water bath for 4 h. The reaction mixture gradually turned red and was left overnight at room temperature. Then the red crystalline pyrazolothiazolidinone (12) was filtered, washed with water and ethanol and crystallised from glacial acetic acid. Similarly, other compounds were also prepared. Their analysis and properties are given in Table 1.

Method B: The compound (12) was also prepared from 2-iminothiazolidinone by refluxing its benzylidene derivative (5) (2 g, 0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml), sodium acetate (2 g) and phenylhydrazine (2 ml) over a wire gauge for 7 h.

It was filtered hot to remove any undissolved substances, cooled, then water was added and boiled for a few minutes when the red crystals of 12 were obtained.

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References

1. R. B. RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1971, 48, 253.
2. F. C. BROWN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1961, 61, 504.
3. B. SAHOO, P. B. TRIPATHI and M. K. ROUT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 36, 421.
4. M. K. ROUT and G. N. MAHAPATRA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2427.
5. T. E. ACHARY, C. S. PANDEY and A. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1065.
6. S. K. MOHANTY, R. SRIDHAR, S. Y. PADMANAVAN, S. RAO and A. S. MITRA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1977, 15, 1146.
7. V. AUWERS, *Chem. Ber.*, 1932, 65, 831.
8. G. AZIZ, M. H. NOSSEIR, N. L. DOSS and A. S. RISK, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1976, 14, 286.
9. S. E. A. MCCALLAN, *Agric. Chem.*, 1947, 2, 31, 45, 67.